

Factors Affecting Organizational Work Conditions on Employee Job Satisfaction: Evidence from the Ethiopian Airline Industry

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ABSTRACT

Job satisfaction among workers is important to customer satisfaction and corporate efficiency in a competitive environment. Workers regard working conditions as key components for their success; require frequent assessments to recognize and enhance factors that are vital to increasing job satisfaction. The goal of the analysis was to investigate the effects of the institutional working conditions on the morale of employees in the airline industry in Ethiopia. The study followed a descriptive-explanatory research methodology, examining a heterogeneous population of 95 from 200 workers of the Ethiopian airline. A self-governing questionnaire was used to collect data; analyzed by means of descriptive and inferential statistics. The research accomplished an 82.11 percent response rate. The findings from the study indicate high correlation coefficients of (0.882) between working conditions and employee job satisfaction. Likewise, there was evidence of a strong and positive correlation between employee job satisfaction and remuneration of (0.831). In addition, proof of a positively correlated elasticity between employee promotion and employee job satisfaction at (0.512). Generally, the total job satisfaction rate in the airline industry was (3.752) out of a total of 5. The three objective factors contributed to 83 percent of differences in the happiness of workers and were, therefore, the key to the satisfaction of employees. In order to improve the job satisfaction of workers, airline management should endeavor to provide training and development programs for staff members to enhance their work skills, and periodically update working conditions and other terms of service; in general, to encourage the process in accordance with industry trends in order to make it more profitable.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Working conditions, Remuneration, Promotion and Employee morale/behavior

INTRODUCTION:

Individuals are the biggest and most treasured asset of any organization. Skilled and motivated individuals create and generate profits from other institutional resources. For instance, physical, monetary and technology. Consequently, any successful entity must not only endeavour to lure skilled workers; it must build and maintain their motivation to work in ever-changing environments. Contented workers are a source of competitive edge. Work performance has been a topic of interest in any business entity. The continued growth and globalization of the airline industry have already caused a great deal of performance management problems; a low level of employee satisfaction and poor service delivery. Significant factors impacting productivity in airline business consist of: long working hours, job stress, low level of care, poor working atmosphere, and fewer benefits for advancement, unequal jobs and low levels of pay. In Ethiopia, the airline industry contributes significantly to income generation for the government. While the very success of airline companies depends on the delivery of reliable service to customers, the goal is to build empowered workers who can promote the initiative [1]. Contented workers will provide good customer service to customers, thereby increasing their commitment to the firm; since customer satisfaction is significant to any organizational success. The

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airline industry relies on workers to accomplish their targets, meaning that management should acknowledge the happiness of staff because the morale of workers is correlated to the quality of service and the success of jobs. Airline companies must therefore recruit, grow, inspire and retain happy workers. This allows administrators to have a better understanding of staff desires, expectations, behavior and worries. Heartfield [2] suggests that, in order to establish an atmosphere for employee retention, it is absolutely vital to understand the most significant determinants of employee job satisfaction and their impacts.

The workplace surroundings are a primary factor in determining reasons for employee engagement and disaffection. Research by Leblebici [3] demonstrates that changing the working conditions decreases grievances and employee turnover thus increasing productivity. Sufficient empirical proof exists to link conditions for workers to employee satisfaction [4,5]. Over recent years, worker's satisfaction at work, measured by the various conditions at work and their surroundings, has been identified as a key factor for determining their performance. The rapid expansion of the aviation industry has caused the current economic boom experienced in Ethiopia. The continued

expansion has also caused plenty of internal management issues, with profound impacts on overall satisfaction. Worker's commitment affects the quality of operation in the aviation industry with a corresponding influence on the level of customer loyalty. Measures to improve employee turnover can, therefore, lead to the creation of happier workers with a positive influence on overall satisfaction. The Aviation industry in Ethiopia encounters a multitude of staff associated problems such as a higher rate of non-attendance, poor management and revenue growth among others; all indicative of low job satisfaction levels. Workplace performance analyses are particularly beneficial. Firms should understand how to handle a diverse team of workers, as it would help to hire and attract qualified employees and maintain a high degree of workplace satisfaction.

The aim of the study was to predict the impact of the organizational working conditions on the happiness of employees in the aviation industry in Ethiopia. The study was conducted on employment conditions, compensation and promotion as key factors impacting the happiness of workers.

Data and Methodology

The analysis followed a descriptive-explanatory inferential statistics; a blend of both descriptive and explanatory research styles. The layout provided a clear definition and evaluation of the indicators used in the study; identified and illustrated their properties and clarified their interaction without distortion as endorsed by [6,7]. The research represented a heterogeneous sample of 95 of the sample population of 200 workers. A moderately-structured, self-governing questionnaire was used to collect data. Prior to the execution of empirical statistical analysis, the questionnaire was pilot-tested and testing for accuracy using Cronbach Alpha, generating a reliability coefficient or elasticity of 0.7912 above the recommended minimum of 0.7 [7,8]. The data gathered were evaluated using descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, and average, to describe the various attributes of the predictors, whereas inferential statistics, particularly, correlation and regression analysis, was used to evaluate the nexus between the selected respondents. Analysis hypotheses were tested using Pearson's Moment of Correlation. In addition, we also performed ANOVA tests to confirm whether the observed model worked whereas the regression test was done to determine the degree to which the model clarified the relationship between the variables.

Results and Discussions

The study had a response rate of 82.11 percent. Among those who replied, 57% were women, while 43% were male, indicating that the bulk of the surveyed workers were female. In comparison, 60 percent of these workers are college graduates with the remaining 40 percent high school graduates.

Working Conditions and Employee Job Satisfaction

The first aim of this analysis was to investigate the effect of working conditions on the productivity and engagement of workers, covering factors such as clarification of goals and priorities, labor relations, the atmosphere at work, and quality and performance management. As per the result, most of the respondents (73 percent) reported that their company has consistent priorities and expectations with an average of 4.315 out of 5. The objectives and priorities of the companies are well articulated and known by all workers as endorsed by 79 percent of the participants. Staff members reverence and support each other on labor relations, backed by 85% of participants with an average score of 4.012 out of 5. Staff members were actively involved in the decision-making process with an average score of 4.001. Likewise, 87 percent of the participants were very pleased with their work. The research also concluded that every worker is treated fairly and with dignity. The findings are consistent with those of Stahl et al. [9] which found that workers favor ties with their employers more than rewards and pay. Administrators are therefore always keen to build a strong working relationship with their employees so as to know their strengths and weaknesses, making it possible for them to use the advantages of their worker's skills for the benefit of the company. It also appeared that developing alliances throughout the enterprise enables workers to reach their career and corporate goals; rendering the workplace more fun, thereby increasing job satisfaction. The study showed that workers did not encounter any kind of misconduct in their jobs, as reported by 85 percent of participants. Similarly, 92 percent of the participants reported a good working relationship in their organization. The analysis of the workplace environment included a series of statements which the participants were asked to show their degree concurrence. The outcome as reported in (Table 1) indicates that 83.34 percent agree to a cheerful and pleasant atmosphere.

Table1. Workplace Environment

Descriptions	Scale										Mean
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	
The atmosphere at the firm is cheerful and pleasant	9	11.5	4	5.12	13	16.67	27	34.62	25	32.05	3.850
Decorations and arrangement of facilities are bright and cheerful	7	8.97	5	6.41	12	15.38	21	26.92	33	42.31	4.321
The firm provides good and safe work conditions	4	5.13	3	3.85	20	25.64	26	33.33	25	32.05	3.832
The firm manager always helps employees when in need	3	3.85	5	6.41	30	38.46	15	19.23	25	32.05	4.208
My office/working space is adequate	4	5.13	1	1.28	21	26.92	24	30.77	28	35.89	3.865
I am provided with adequate working tools	8	10.26	7	8.97	13	16.67	29	37.18	21	26.92	3.713

Note: (1-5) indicates strongly disagree, disagree, Somehow agree, Agree and strongly agree, respectively; (a) and (b) also represents frequency and percentage, respectively.

Typically, all measurements of the working environment have high average values. This implies that the workers are happier with their working environment. This finding is inconsonant with the outcome of [10-12]. Who claims that employees would favor working under conditions with higher environmental convenience and comfort. The neglect of such employment conditions, among other factors, can have a detrimental effect on the physically and psychologically well-being of employees. Singh and Jain [13] also suggest that workers can use poor conditions as a justification to return to administration because they may believe that leadership does not respect or accept their contributions and work done. The consequence of such claims is that companies must always strive to maintain better working conditions in order to mitigate such misunderstandings between workers in an attempt to improve their job satisfaction over time as reported by [14].

As per the findings in (Table 2), the aviation industry had a clear focus on providing good quality service as sponsored, a high level of participation of workers in giving feedback on how to increase quality of service, a desire to engage honestly with customers and consider their expectations; Each with average scores of more than 3.91 from a total of 5, indicating that the quality of service was very good.

Table2. Quality of Service

Descriptions	Scale										Mean
	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	
My airline company has a strong focus on the provision of quality service to a customer	6	7.69	2	2.56	3	3.85	35	44.87	32	41.03	4.211
My firm encourages employees to give suggestions on how to improve quality	8	10.26	7	8.97	11	14.10	23	29.49	29	37.18	3.912
I am allowed to freely interact with customers to understand their requirements	2	2.56	10	12.82	0	0	30	38.46	36	46.15	4.532

Note: (1-5) indicates strongly disagree, disagree, Somehow agree, Agree and strongly agree, respectively; (a) and (b) also represents frequency and percentage, respectively.

In terms of performance management practices, most airline companies stressed and encouraged cooperation (90 percent) and valued healthy competition in the workforce (88 percent). In fact, 85% of participants indicated that airline firms had a fair and consistent appraisal process for all workers. There was a consistent information exchange sharing at all grades, backed by (84.61 percent) of participants. Many of the participants (95 percent) definitely knew what was required of them and got daily input on their results (89 percent). Daily professional development programs have been given to help enhance their ability and to identify exceptional performance. The findings also indicate that airline companies appreciated and respected the jobs of their workers (85%). Likewise, 78 percent of participants reported that they had received substantial bonuses for a job well done. These findings are similar to studies demonstrating that appreciation of work performance through praise, reward and bonuses are economical ways to increase profitability, staff morale and competitiveness [9,15]. Management appreciation of worker's ability to do the job is often highly valued as a component of employee job satisfaction [9].

The research allowed participants to score on a scale of 1-5 their level of agreement on the argument that, "in particular, airline companies have produced better working environments"; 25 percent of participants somehow agreed, 48 percent agreed and 27 percent strongly agreed. This suggests that all participants thought that the terms of working conditions in the aviation sector were favorable. Thus, in conclusion, the research confirmed overall worker job satisfaction based on favorable working environments. The study demonstrated a strong positive association of (0.882) between working environments and workplace performance with a P-value of 0.0000. Displaying a significant level of 1 percent between the selected predictors. Therefore, the study fails to accept the null hypothesis of "working condition has no significant impact on worker job satisfaction in airline industry in Ethiopia".

Compensation and Worker Job Satisfaction

The second objective of this analysis was to examine the complex effect of the remuneration of workers on the job quality of employees. Different aspects of compensation in the airline industry have been investigated and their influence on job satisfaction measured. In particular, the study found that there was a high sense of satisfaction with the compensation plan (income and benefits) in the airline industry, as indicated by 83 percent of the participants. The degree of satisfaction was evaluated by a series of statements on different elements of compensation in which participants were asked to show on a scale of 1-5 the degree at which they agreed or disagree with each of the statements.

As per the outcome reported in (Table 3), 74.35 percent of the participant agreed that the basic salary of the aviation industry is reasonable. Similarly, 72.10 percent were of the view that they were adequately compensated for their hard work. In

addition, the analysis concluded that pay and benefits are directly proportional to the skills and experience of workers. Employees believed they received a fair salary based on their level of responsibility as reported by 78.21 percent of the participants. The study showed a high level of employer commitment, with 79.49 percent of the participants suggesting that they cannot take a job in other airline firms since they were sufficiently compensated. Workers receive incentives for an excellent performance. In addition, most of the participants were satisfied with the incentive system of the firm. Reporting 73.53 percent. 65.38 percent of the participants were of the view that the same number of workers earned the same wage and that the company had equal opportunities for each worker as shown by 62.82 percent of the participants. Generally, there was strong satisfaction with all facets of compensation, as shown by the high average score of more than 3.1 out of 5 (Table 3), indicating that the majority of workers in the airline industry in Ethiopia were satisfied with their pay packages.

Table3. Compensation aspect in the Airline Industry

Descriptions	Scale										Mean
	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	
The basic salary is reasonable	10	12.82	10	12.82	12	15.38	28	35.89	18	23.08	3.315
I am adequately remunerated for my efforts.	11	14.10	9	11.54	16	20.51	25	32.05	17	21.79	3.432
My pay and benefits are commensurate with my skills and experience.	6	7.69	11	14.10	9	11.54	30	38.46	22	28.21	3.938
My Salary is fair compared to other staff with the same level responsibility.	11	14.10	8	10.26	15	19.23	23	29.49	21	26.92	3.113
I cannot seek employment in another firm because what I am paid currently is adequate	16	20.51	2	2.56	17	21.79	23	29.49	22	28.21	3.245
I received other benefits such as bonus when performance is good	14	17.95	3	3.85	19	24.36	32	41.03	10	12.82	3.415
The airline company benefit system is perfect	14	17.95	7	8.97	18	23.08	25	32.05	14	17.95	3.312
Same level of employees received the same salary	13	16.67	14	17.95	12	15.38	21	26.92	18	23.08	3.331
Airline firms provide equal benefits for every employee	11	14.10	18	23.08	5	6.41	29	37.18	15	19.23	3.30

Note: (1-5) indicates strongly disagree, disagree, Somehow agree, Agree and strongly agree, respectively; (a) and (b) also represents frequency and percentage, respectively.

The study also showed a very high (91%) level of job satisfaction among workers due to compensation in the airline industry in Ethiopia. The study further established a robust positive association of (0.831) amid remuneration and the degree of job satisfaction with a P-value of 0.0000. Displaying a significant level of 1 percent between the selected predictors. Therefore, the study fails to accept the null hypothesis that "*remuneration does not significantly affect worker job satisfaction* in the airline industry in Ethiopia".

The findings clearly demonstrate that workers enjoy a reasonable remuneration scheme in the airline industry in Ethiopia, thus adding greatly to their work satisfaction. The findings are consistent with Oshagbemi [16] analysis of UK researchers, which identified a significant statistical correlation between compensation and employee engagement. Stahl et al. [9] also claims that pay has sometimes stayed one of the top five key significant factors of worker satisfaction at work; more than job security and direct interaction with leadership. In favor of this argument, Silva [17] suggests that if incomes are not consumer-related, this can lead to frustration and resentment on the ground that worker's skills and experience are not compatible with the compensation they earn.

Promotion and Worker Job Satisfaction

The third objective of this analysis seeks to investigate the determinants affecting the promotion of employee job satisfaction in the airline industry in Ethiopia, by evaluating the various facets of promotion, along with their influence on employee job satisfaction. The participants agreed with the idea that "the airline industry has developed and enforced an equal, balanced and adequate promotion scheme" (78 percent), indicating that most airline companies have built and implemented a perfectly honest, balanced and sufficient promotion program. (Table 4) presents the outcome with respect to the various aspect of promotion; the promotion regulations and criteria were very explicit (80.78 percent), the promotion was focused on the quality of workers (58.97 percent), the airline company had a flawless promotion appraisal process (74.35 percent) and every worker had the chance of receiving promotion at the firm (70.51 percent). In contrast, 55.12 percent of the participant confirmed that promotion is based on the manager's decision, indicating their level of dissatisfaction. The study also found that senior staff had benefits in promotion relative to their subordinate peers, as reported by (64.1 percent) of the participants. While (62.82 percent) of participants thought that the promotion in airline companies was equal to all staff, (57.69 percent) suggested that it relied on one's relationship with the director. As shown by (67.95 percent) of the participants, the job performance assessment

carried out by managers was fair and focused on consistent performance requirements. Overall, workers were pleased with the airline promotion policy (64.19 percent) and that reward incentives strengthened their job attitudes (83.34 percent).

Table4. Promotion and Employee Job Satisfaction

Descriptions	Scale										Mean
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	
Promotion rules and requirement very clear	6	7.69	9	11.54	23	29.49	18	23.08	22	28.21	3.519
Promotion depend on employee's work performance	13	16.67	19	24.36	14	17.95	25	32.05	7	8.97	2.989
Promotion depends on the managers decisions	14	17.95	21	26.92	11	14.10	7	8.97	25	32.05	2.842
The airline company has a perfect evaluation system for promotion	5	6.41	15	19.23	26	33.33	16	20.51	16	20.51	3.521
Every employee have opportunity to get promotion.	16	20.51	7	8.97	19	24.36	24	30.77	12	15.38	3.232
Senior employees get advantage in promotion	13	16.67	15	19.23	10	12.82	19	24.36	21	26.92	2.853
Promotion is fair to all employees	15	19.23	14	17.95	17	21.79	23	29.49	9	11.54	2.842
Promotion depends on employee relationship with the manager	17	21.79	16	20.51	16	20.51	10	12.82	19	24.36	3.147
Job performance evaluation done by my supervisor is fair and based on clear performance standard	6	7.69	19	24.36	17	21.79	9	11.54	27	34.62	3.287
I am satisfied with the firms promotion policy	15	19.23	13	16.67	11	14.10	19	24.36	20	25.64	2.912
Promotion can improve my work attitude	5	6.41	8	10.26	15	19.23	27	34.62	23	29.49	3.819

Note: (1-5) indicates strongly disagree, disagree, Somehow agree, Agree and strongly agree, respectively; (a) and (b) also represents frequency and percentage, respectively.

The mean marks on all promotion criteria were above average, ranging from 2.842 to 3.819; indicating that the participants agreed with all components of the promotion that were measured. On the basis of the findings, it is evident that promotion had an influence on the morale of workers at work. Nonetheless, 54.5 percent of the participants were unhappy with the job satisfaction of the workers due to the promotion, while 45.5 percent were happy and content; indicated a high level of discontent with the promotion system in the airline industry. The degree of promotion has a greater effect on job satisfaction relative to appreciation and accomplishment. It is on the basis that the promotion to the next tier would result in significant improvements in pay, independence, and supervision. This, therefore, implies that the lack of proper incentives for advancement or the existence of disciplinary conditions that are not satisfactory to workers would create discontent between employees. Correlation testing was used to determine the association between promotion and worker contentment; a positive correlation of 0.512 with a P-value of 0.0000 was observed. This means that staff promotion had a positive impact on the morale of workers at work. Thus, the study fails to accept the null hypothesis that "promotion has no significant effect on worker job satisfaction in the airline industry in Ethiopia"

Overall Worker Job Satisfaction in the Airline Industry

On a scale of 1–5, participants were asked to show their level of job satisfaction with respect to the various predictors or indicators; while 19 percent of respondents classified their job satisfaction as low, 38 percent scored it somehow high, 40 percent scored it high, and 3 percent scored it very high. This means that a lot of airline workers are happy with their employers, with an average mean of 3.522.

Regression Analysis

In this study, a regression analysis was adopted to investigate the dynamic effect of remuneration, workplace conditions and promotion as explanatory variables on worker or employee job satisfaction as the response variable in the airline industry in Ethiopia. With reference to the finding shown in (Table 5), employment conditions, remuneration, and promotion jointly recorded 88 percent influence on employee job satisfaction with R-Square of 0.751 in the airline industry in Ethiopia. The findings further suggest that the calculation of employee satisfaction at work using the model can only be underestimated by 0.31 percent.

Table5. Regression Model Summary

Model	Elasticity	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error
(a)	0.882	0.751	0.742	0.3114

In a similar manner, the study performed the ANOVA test during the empirical analysis. The outcome of the test as represented in (Table 6) discloses an F-statistics of 82.312 with a p-value of 0.0002. This indicates a significance level of 1 percent. This implies that the explanatory variables significantly contribute to the variation in the response variable. This outcome is inconsonant with the findings recommended by [18] in their study by establishing a positive significant relationship amid organizational and behavioural indicators and environmental conditions on worker or employee job performance. In conclusion, the study suggests that if workers are handled equally and fairly and adequately monitored, their level of job satisfaction can be improved.

Table6. ANOVA Results

Model		Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F-statistic	p-value
(a)	Regression	34.121	4	8.530	82.312	0.0002
	Residual	7.112	74	0.096		
	Total	41.233	78			

As pointed out in (Table 7), a 1 percent increase in working conditions, remuneration and promotion are associated with an increase in workers job satisfaction by 0.322, 0.251 and 0.135 percent, respectively.

Table6. Regression coefficients

Model	Un-Standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T-Statistics	P-value
	B	Standard Error	Beta		
Working conditions	0.322	0.054	0.413	5.963	0.0002***
Remuneration	0.251	0.132	0.321	1.902	0.0000***
Promotion	0.135	0.069	0.257	1.957	0.0000***
Constant	0.411	0.221		1.859	0.0000***

Note: *** indicates a significant level of 1%

Conclusions and Policy implications

Generally speaking, the total level of job satisfaction among workers in the airline industry is high as a result of favorable working conditions, a reasonable compensation plan, and a decent, inclusive and adequate promotion process. Many airline staff is inclined to continue serving in their respective companies without seeking employment somewhere. The reality that most airline companies had specific goals and priorities that were well articulated and acknowledged making it possible for workers to remain focused and strive towards the accomplishment of the goals set. The business environment in the majority of airline companies in Ethiopia is favorable, distinguished by a friendly and welcoming atmosphere, bright and colorful decorations, good organization of equipment and sufficient workspace; all of which have a beneficial effect on the morale of workers at work. Airline companies in Ethiopia have a reasonable remuneration plan (salaries and benefits) corresponding with the skills and experience of workers, which has a positive influence on the job satisfaction of workers. Most airline companies have developed and enforced an equal, balanced and adequate promotion process, distinguished by a perfect appraisal system, consistent promotion rules, and specifications. Although every worker had the chance to receive a promotion, this relied largely on the judgment of the boss. The promotion of workers was also positively correlated and had a significant impact on the happiness of workers at work. The study confirmed that the various predictors contribute largely to employee job satisfaction. Nevertheless, the job condition accounts for the largest effect, while promotion had the least effect on the satisfaction of workers among the three determinant variables.

Likewise, the research also identified a number of areas of the occupational working conditions needing consideration in an attempt to improve the job satisfaction of workers in the airline industry in Ethiopia. First, Airline management must provide its staff with equal opportunities for training

and development in order to help boost their potential for efficient service quality and satisfaction. While most airline companies have fair, equal opportunities and effective promotion structure, there is a need for airline management to set up a committee to oversee promotion rather than depending on the judgment of the director alone. Airline leadership must periodically review workers' salaries and benefits and ensure that they are entirely consistent with their skills and work experience, similar to the general practice of the industry; as this would raise their morale and increase their performance.

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